

Amphibian Recording Status Update for 2009

Prepared for:
Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative
Appalachian Mountain Club, Worcester Chapter
White Mountain National Forest
Friends of Wachusett Mountain

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Amphibians are very sensitive to temperature, moisture, and environmental contamination. This group provides an excellent opportunity to track population and community ecology in sensitive ecological systems where amphibians occupy several niches. Studying populations is important to predict trends, both positive (increase) and negative (extirpation). Documenting amphibian breeding phenology and reproductive effort will provide excellent reference data for long-term studies of how frog communities respond to environmental variability. I predict that research on population and reproductive biology of amphibians will be more likely to detect changes at one of these study sites because each represents the extreme limits of New England habitat zones. Moreover isolated populations are likely to have a faster rate of selection compared to mainland, more panmictic, populations where subtle effects of selection pressure are not exacerbated, but diluted through the larger gene pool.

Study locations were selected based on occurrence of a fishless pond where amphibians had been previously observed breeding and calling. The three study sites include one pond on Nantucket Island (low elevation, low latitude), near the summit of Wachusett Mountain (mid elevation, mid latitude) in central Massachusetts, and Hermit Lake (high elevation, high altitude) on Mount Washington, NH.

In 2008-2009 I installed digital recording equipment (Song Meter, Wildlife Acoustics, Inc.) to monitor calling frogs at three locations within New England to begin year 1 of a long-term study. The objective is to determine how reproductive effort of different species of frogs varies across New England within one season and how those same frogs vary from season to season.

Recording devices were set to record for 30 minutes every evening beginning at approximately 2100 h. Temperature loggers (iButton) were also installed at each study site to record water surface temperature (~12 cm from the surface) and another taped to the underside of the recording devices (Song Meter by Wildlife Acoustics, Inc.).

The Song Meters were not installed until late May or early June so the early spring amphibians were not recorded at lower latitude and lower elevation sites (wood frog and spring peeper). The dates on which each site was sampled and species of frog or toad documented calling are listed below:

Squam Farm, Nantucket, MA
El. 9 m, 41 18' 37.87" N 69 59' 58.48" W
May 19; June 10-October 11, 2009
spring peeper, green frog

Wachusett Mountain, Princeton, MA
El. 600 m, 42 29' 20.45" N 71 53' 13.32" W
June 12-October 5, 2009
Gray tree frogs

Hermit Lake, Mount Washington, Sargent's Purchase, NH
El. 1180 m, 44 15' 38.65" N 71 17' 8.82" W
June 6-July 19; July 30-August 12; August 28-October 29, 2009
Spring peepers, American toads, wood frog, green frog

As expected, the species calling at each location are not as interesting as the phenology of breeding. Specifically, spring peepers call until the end of July at the high elevation, high latitude site at Hermit Lake. There were several lone males calling into the first few days of August, but after that it seems the peepers were done calling. The Nantucket and Wachusett peepers were finished calling at the end of May. However, because the recording did not begin until early June, therefore, this deduction is based on the presumption that these species were done calling by that time because they were mostly absent from the recordings starting in early June.

Technical Details: I consider 2009 a test year for the Song Meters and a lesson that programming devices and software can be challenging and time consuming. Each unit had to be programmed for its latitude and longitude to synchronize the internal clock with the sunrise and sunsets at each respective location, which I had trouble setting up correctly on some units so programmed for daily fixed-time recording. I worked with the Maria Mitchell Association, Mount Washington Observatory, and Friends of Wachusett Mountain to periodically swap data cards at each of the study ponds. At Hermit Lake, one of the cards filled up before it could be replaced so there is a void in the data during the summer. In October the units were removed from all locations.

The 8 GB SD cards used to store data needed to be swapped with a empty replacement cards approximately every month. Now that I have a higher confidence in programming the Song Meters, I shall increase the size of the SD cards (16 or 32GB) and allow the unit to run longer periods without maintenance. I also realized the digital space required to store the recorded data mandated the

need to purchase a backup drive. Once all the data were consolidated and stored, I began experimenting with the song recognition software (Song Scope) and I continue to work on developing species-specific frog call recognizers. Once I have these functioning, I can more efficiently quantify breeding effort of each species each night. These results will then be used to track how breeding is linked to temperature and precipitation for each species at each location. I am currently searching for an institution that could store these digital audio files and data so that it is available to future researchers.

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